

High-Efficiency Photothermal Water Evaporation using Broadband Solar Energy Harvesting by Ultrablack Silicon Structures

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Development of broadband absorption materials for solar energy harvesting is an important strategy to address global energy issues. Herein, it is demonstrated that an ultrablack silicon structure with abundant surface texturing can absorb about 98.7% solar light within the wavelength range of 300 to 2500 nm, i.e., a very large range and amount. Under 1 sun irradiation, the ultrablack silicon sample's surface temperature can increase from 21.2 to 51.2 °C in 15 min. During the photothermal water evaporation process, the ultrablack silicon sample's surface temperature can still reach a highest temperature of 43.2 °C. The average photothermal conversion efficiency (PTCE) can be as high as 72.96%. The excellent photothermal performance to the excellent light-trapping ability of the pyramidal surface nanostructures during solar illumination, which leads to extremely efficient absorption of light, is attributed. In addition, the large water contact area also enables fast vapor transport. The stability of the photothermal converter is also examined, presenting excellent structure and performance stabilities over 10 cycles. This indicates that the ultrablack Si absorber can be a promising photothermal conversion material for seawater desalination, water purification, photothermal therapy, and more.

1. Introduction

Solar energy conversion is one of the hottest topics to address the global energy challenge, and lots of scientists have been contributing to searching for new materials for broadband solar energy harvesting due to the inexhaustible source of solar energy.^[1–10] Solar to heat conversion, also called photothermal conversion, is one of the most important forms among the solar energy conversions, in addition to Si-based photovoltaic cell, perovskite solar cell, photoelectrochemical water splitting, and so on.^[11–19] It also ensures wide spread applications including photothermal imaging, seawater desalination, and photothermo-electric conversion.^[20–24] Photothermal water evaporation is of great significance to take full advantage of solar energy without any other energy input. However, most of the reported materials have more or less problems toward gaining high quality and high efficiency for photothermal water purification or desalination.

For example, Xu et al. reported cotton–CuS nanocage–agarose aerogel showing a high photothermal conversion efficiency (PTCE) of 94.9% under 1.0 sun for the application in water evaporation.^[18] Unfortunately, Cu can be toxic and harmful to human health. Zhu et al. reported that graphene oxide-based aerogels presented a relatively low PTCE of 83% under 1.0 sun due to a lower solar absorption of about 92% from solar wavelength 200 to 2500 nm.^[25] Thus, it is still a challenge to develop a photothermal conversion system with nontoxicity, high efficiency, and ultrahigh light absorption capability across the whole solar spectrum.^[23,26,27]

One possible solution is to design a photothermal system that is capable of addressing the aforementioned concerns. Several principles should be considered.^[19,28,29] First, the photothermal material must show a broadband absorption.^[19] To ensure a high PTCE, an overall absorption above 97% in the wavelength range from 300 to 2500 nm is expected. At the same time, the average absorption ability of this material toward solar light should be as high as possible.^[25,27,30,31] Second, the water uptake part should have a certain degree of thermal-insulating to avoid thermal loss.^[19] Then, there should be enough water transportation

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channels for water vapor transporting for efficient evaporation. Furthermore, the evaporated water must not contain any toxic elements from the photothermal system. Finally, the applied materials must be earth-abundant and affordable for large-scale industrial applications.^[19,27,28,30]

In this article, we report a nontoxic, highly efficient, low-cost, and broadband absorptive photothermal converter. Using the reactive ion etching (RIE) method, we prepare an ultrablack silicon (ub-Si) sample with a super high solar absorption capability of about 98.7% across the wavelength from 300 to 2500 nm.^[32] This result indicates a better advantage than the reported photothermal materials. By combining the ub-Si with a superhydrophilic porous sponge (SPS) as a photothermal converter, we achieve a high PTCE of about 72.96% under the AM 1.5G of 100 mW cm⁻² solar intensity. Finite difference time domain (FDTD) simulation results confirm that the light absorption of ub-Si surface nanostructure is very high due to the improved electric field enhancement (EFE) within the ub-Si structures. In addition, multiple reflections and free carrier absorption are also important factors according to our previous work.^[32]

2. Results and Discussion

In a typical ub-Si preparation experiment, ub-Si nanostructures with broadband light absorption performance are controlled by the etching time using the RIE method. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) images with the same magnification present different sizes and densities as the etching time increases from

20 to 120 min (Figure S1, Supporting Information). In Figure S2, Supporting Information, pristine Si sample shows the highest reflectance among the different etching time of Si samples. Once the Si samples are etched, a sharp decrease appears for the Si sample with an etching time of 20 min. For longer etching times, the reflectance of Si samples gradually reduces and the sample with an etching time of 120 min shows the lowest reflectance, which indicates that this sample gains the best solar energy harvesting capability among all Si samples. Therefore, the ub-Si sample with an etching time of 120 min is chosen for the photothermal conversion experiments. For this sample, also more detailed SEM and transmission electron microscope (TEM) characterizations have been conducted. As shown in **Figure 1a–c**, the top view of the ub-Si surface distributes quantities of highly uniformed micro/nanostructures. The micro/nanostructures of vertical and horizontal lengths have a large range from several hundred nanometers to more than one micrometer. **Figure 1d–f** shows the side view of as-prepared ub-Si with abundant surface texturing, which indicates their 3D structures and looks like rolling hills of different sizes. The cross section SEM images of the as-prepared ub-Si micro/nanostructure (like “mountainous hills”) with different magnifications are shown in **Figure S3**, Supporting Information. The largest hill shows a size with a horizontal length of about 1.6 μm and a vertical length of about 2.5 μm, from which we can also observe some nanostructures. All the SEM characterizations confirm that relative larger size hills gain the longer light travel distance and thus lead to multiple forward

Figure 1. a–c) Top view SEM images of the as-prepared ub-Si micro/nanostructure at different scales. d–h) Side view SEM images at a tilt angle of 20° of the as-prepared ub-Si micro/nanostructure at different magnifications. g) TEM image of a pyramidal ub-Si micro/nanostructure lying on a TEM grid. h) Close-up TEM micrograph of the blue-marked square in (g). i) HRTEM image of the blue-marked rectangle in (h). The two yellow dashed lines delimit the native oxide layer of the monocrystalline silicon. The inset shows the corresponding FFT pattern.

scatterings as well as light localization, which should be responsible for nearly perfect light-harvesting capability.^[30,33] Figure 1g shows a Si pyramid lying on a TEM grid, which is scratched from the ub-Si sample. Figure 1h shows the TEM image of the enlarged area in Figure 1g's blue rectangle. We observe some nanostructures on the Si pyramid. The high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) picture in Figure 1i verifies that the monocrystalline silicon is surrounded by a native oxide layer with a thickness of several nanometers. The corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) pattern indicates its good single crystallinity. A larger sized HRTEM image is shown in Figure S4, Supporting Information, where about 5 nm oxide layer can be observed.

Single crystalline silicon has a typical sp^3 hybrid diamond structure with a lattice constant of 0.543 nm. As shown in Figure 2a, one silicon atom is equally connected to four other silicon atoms by covalent bonding. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Raman measurements are conducted to investigate the crystalline structure of the pristine Si and ub-Si samples. Figure 2b shows the XRD patterns of the pristine Si and ub-Si samples. Both samples show the strongest peak intensity at 69.3° of the (400) reflection, which indicates good monocrystallinity before and after etching^[32,34,35] and is confirmed by Raman

measurements (Figure 2c). The strongest vibration at 520 cm^{-1} show Si-Si bond vibrations.^[36] Because of the strong field enhancement (see FDTD simulation later) leading to strong light absorption, the Raman intensity of ub-Si is obviously lower than the pristine one.

Figure 2d shows the mechanism of how typical ub-Si micro/nanostructure materials transfer solar energy to heat.^[5,19,27,29] By creating a micro/nanostructure on a flat silicon surface, the optical path length is increased, yielding a stronger light absorption. When the incident light wavelength is similar to the size of the micro/nanostructure, light can be largely scattered (Mie scattering). Multiple scattering can even occur in the pyramidal nanostructures and light can be strongly trapped, leading to a largely reduced reflection. As a result, solar energy can be largely harvested through a highly enhanced PTCE. Heteroatom doping for broadband light absorption is a good approach to enhance the PTCE. As shown in Figure 2e, highly B-doped Si shows a nearly perfect absorption in the full solar spectrum with an average absorption of about 98.7%. The total reflectance is shown in Figure S2, Supporting Information, showing a reflectance of $\approx 1\%$, which is much lower than the pristine Si sample. It is clearly observed that the pristine Si wafer looks like a mirror

Figure 2. a) Schematic diagram of the silicon crystal structure from z axis. b) XRD patterns of the pristine Si sample and ub-Si sample. c) Raman measurements of the pristine Si sample and ub-Si sample. d) Schematic diagram of how the heat produces during the light interacting with the ub-Si. e) Absorbance of the ub-Si sample from wavelength 300 to 2500 nm. The inset is AM 1.5G solar spectrum. f) ub-Si surface temperature changes by time when lighting on or off the Xe lamp under an optical density of 100 mW cm^{-2} (1 sun). g) The real-time ub-Si surface temperatures are monitored by an IR camera at the first 15 min in (f).

due to higher reflection while only the black surface can be seen on the ub-Si wafer because of extremely low reflection (Figure S5, Supporting Information). According to a previous work,^[37] strong doping helps to improve the absorption of light with wavelength beyond the band edge (1110 nm), whereas lightly doped Si showed a large reflection when the solar light wavelength exceeds 1110 nm (Si's cutoff wavelength). Combining aforementioned results with the previous characterization, it indicates that doping and nanostructuring can be an effective approach to harvest more solar energy and further to obtain a high PTCE.^[17,38] It is noted that the nearly full solar spectrum absorption performance of ub-Si stands forward among the reported full solar spectrum absorption materials (see Table 1).^[17,18,21,23,30,31]

In a typical photothermal responsive experiment, a $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ ub-Si sample is used to explore the sample's surface temperature change under an intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} (AM 1.5G). Figure 2f shows that the rising rate of ub-Si surface temperature becomes slower and slower due to thermal equilibrium with the

environment. It takes about 15 min to achieve 51.2°C from room temperature (21.2°C), whereas it lasts the same time to cool down to 22.2°C again. It can be directly observed that the ub-Si surface temperature changes by time according to Figure 2g. The real-time infrared (IR) images indicate that the ub-Si sample's temperature increases with illumination time. After $t = 15 \text{ min}$, the ub-Si sample reaches the highest temperature of 51.2°C , which proves its good photothermal conversion capability. When switching off the lamp, the cooling to room temperature requires about 15 min, indicating the thermal conduction of the ub-Si to the beaker and air.

Figure 3a shows the schematic diagram of the photothermal water evaporation experimental setup. As shown in Figure 3b, the ub-Si with an area of $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ was directly placed on the center of water-saturated sponge ($3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$). Figure 3c shows the photo of ub-Si sample with a size of $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$. Under the solar light irradiation, the ub-Si sample absorbs the solar energy and converts it to heat. The heat then is transferred to the sponge uptaking with water for the generation of water vapor.

The sponge has a multifunction: first of all, it is used as a water absorber, which can uptake enough liquid water for generating water vapor. Then, it functions as a supporting material for holding the ub-Si sample. Last but not least, it also offers plenty of channels for transporting water vapor to the atmosphere. In Figure 3d, it is an optical microscope (OM) image of the multifunction sponge. In this scale, we can observe lots of microporous structures with pore size from dozens of micrometers to several hundred micrometers. The more detailed microstructure characterization about the porous sponge by means of SEM and OM is shown in Figure S6 and S7, Supporting Information. To measure the wettability of the porous sponge, contact angle (CA) measurement has been conducted. As shown in Figure 3e,f,

Table 1. Absorption performance compared to recently reported photothermal conversion materials.

Samples	Average absorptance	Absorption range	References
ub-Si	98.7%	300–2500 nm	This work
3D Al nanoparticles	<90%	400–2500 nm	ref. [17]
Cotton–CuS aerogel	95.5%	290–1400 nm	ref. [18]
PCC sponge	96%	250–2500 nm	ref. [21]
GO-based aerogels	<90%	200–2500 nm	ref. [23]
Te nanoparticles	≈90%	200–2000 nm	ref. [30]
3D graphene	97%	250–2500 nm	ref. [31]

Figure 3. a) Schematic picture of the photothermal water evaporation experimental setup. b) The photothermal water evaporation device, the ub-Si sample is put on the center of the sponge's surface, and the sponge is placed in water with exposing about 20% of its body into the air. c) Photo of $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ ub-Si sample, which is used as a solar absorber. d) OM image of the porous sponge, which is acted as a water transportation channel, supporting material, and also water vapor transportation channel. e,f) CA measurement before and after the test.

Figure 4. a) Real-time IR images during the photothermal water evaporation; the number at the top left shows the maximum value of the temperature in the black rectangle. b) Temperature changes against time with and without illumination. c) Mass change of water evaporation with SPS and ub-Si@SPS under the dark, 100 mW cm^{-2} , 300 mW cm^{-2} . d) ub-Si@SPS sample cycle tests of PTCE under the solar illumination intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} . e) The XRD patterns before and after cycle tests. No changes appear in the patterns, showing the stable microstructure in ub-Si.

we capture the image of the droplet under the porous sponge before the droplet touches the sponge's surface. Upon the droplet reaches the sponge's surface, it is suddenly absorbed by the porous sponge and forms a nearly 0° CA. Here, we call the "porous sponge" "SPS." We also measure the SPS water uptake capability, Figure S8a and S8b, Supporting Information, show the weights of SPS before and after soaking saturated water. It indicates that a saturated sponge (16.052 g) can absorb water exceeding 20 times the weight of the dry sponge (0.768 g). This only causes a part of expansion (see Figure S9a and S9b, Supporting Information). Thus, the evaporation occurs mainly from the sponge. But, the effective evaporation cannot be expected in the area of sponge covered with black Si.

However, vapor transport can be imagined through the channels of the porous structure into the uncovered area of the sponge. The effective evaporation area is considered as $(3 \times 3 - 2 \times 2) \text{ cm}^2$. In addition, it is possible to design a container to collect condensed water from the evaporated water vapor.^[17] Thus, it shows a great potential application for photothermal seawater desalination by only taking advantage of solar energy. Figure 3b shows the photothermal water evaporation device. The ub-Si, as a solar light absorber, is placed on the top of the sponge.

The PTCE is evaluated by the water evaporation rate and the increased water temperature in an hour compared with the initial situation. Figure 4a shows the real-time temperature change of

the whole photothermal device under an intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} (AM 1.5G). At the beginning, the ub-Si sample's surface shows an initial temperature of 22.5°C . In the end, the ub-Si sample's surface reaches 43.2°C after 1 h illumination, which is 20.7°C higher than the initial temperature. Due to thermal diffusion to the water and SPS, the ub-Si sample's surface temperature with an hour's irradiation is even 8°C lower than that for the pure ub-Si (Figure 2g). It verifies that ub-Si not only has an excellent photothermal conversion ability but also can transfer the heat to the water and the sponge and thus speed up the water evaporation process. It should be noted that only the ub-Si sample gains the highest temperature surface while the temperature of the other part remains relatively low. This is probably caused by the strong EFE within the ub-Si sample (see the FDTD simulation later). Figure 4b shows the ub-Si's surface temperature change during the photothermal water evaporation under the irradiation. It shows a similar increase in the whole process compared to the bare ub-Si.

In the water evaporation experiments, the evaporation rate is used to calculate the efficiency. It defines as^[18,25,27,39]

$$r = \frac{m_{\text{start}} - m_{\text{end}}}{S_{\text{effe}} \cdot t_{\text{illum}}} \quad (1)$$

where r stands for the average evaporation rate in 1 h, m_{start} and m_{end} for recording the mass at t min, $t + 5$ min. t_{illum} is 1 h. S_{effe} is the effective area of SPS not covered by ub-Si ($3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2 - 2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$), respectively. During the illumination, we record the mass of water evaporation by a balance, which is shown in Figure 4c. The evaporation rate of ub-Si@SPS shows about $0.08 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in the dark. The evaporation from the ub-Si@SPS combination under 100 mW cm^{-2} is much faster and can reach the evaporation rate to $1.16 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, which is about 14.5 times than that in the dark. The evaporation rate is a constant in the observed time frame (in Figure 4c). We define the PTCE as

$$\eta_{\text{PTCE}} = [r \cdot \Delta H_{\text{Eva}} + c_p \cdot r \cdot (T_2 - T_1)] / Q_{\text{in}} \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_{Eva} represents the water of evaporation enthalpy, here $\Delta H_{\text{Eva}} \approx 2.43 \times 10^3 \text{ J g}^{-1}$ at 30°C , c_p is the specific heat of water, T_1 and T_2 stand for the initial and final temperature of water, and Q_{in} is input power of solar light on the ub-Si sample. In this case, Q_{in} is calculated to be per 1 m^2 and for per 1 h irradiation, $Q_{\text{in}} = 1 \text{ kW h m}^{-2}$ ($3.6 \times 10^6 \text{ J m}^{-2}$). Due to $r \Delta H_{\text{Eva}} \gg c_p r(T_2 - T_1)$, $c_p r(T_2 - T_1)$ can be neglected in the equation. Thus

$$\eta_{\text{PTCE}} = r \Delta H_{\text{Eva}} / Q_{\text{in}} \quad (3)$$

The results show that the η_{PTCE} of ub-Si@SPS under AM 1.5G 100 mW cm^{-2} irradiation can reach 72.96%. We think two essential factors should be responsible for such high PTCE: 1) the ub-Si has an extremely excellent light absorption structure so that nearly all the solar light can be absorbed to produce heat. 2) SPS offers enough channels for water vapor transportation. The photothermal water evaporation experiment under a solar intensity of 300 mW cm^{-2} is also explored. Figure 4c also indicates an average evaporation rate of $1.68 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, which is 1.45 times higher than that under

100 mW cm^{-2} . This can be a good path to improve the evaporation rate. However, it only gains a $\eta_{\text{PTCE}} = 36.0\%$. We assume that high flux solar light can be rapidly absorbed by ub-Si, but the heat can be dissipated into the air in a larger scale, leading to lower efficiency.

To explore the stability of the as-prepared ub-Si@SPS, the cycle test, reflection and absorption properties, crystal structure, and morphological characterization before and after photothermal water evaporation experiments have been conducted. As shown in Figure 4d, the ub-Si@SPS behaves good stability after 10 cycle tests. Because it keeps high PTCE (average 73.04%) during the 10 cycle tests. This can be an excellent advantage for water evaporation of the ub-Si@SPS system. The reflectance (Figure S10, Supporting Information) characterizations also verify it. There are almost no declines in both reflectance and absorptance performance after the ub-Si@SPS sample is tested under a solar intensity of 100 mW cm^{-2} for ten times. Figure 4e shows that the peaks of single crystalline Si (100) still stand at the position of 69.3° before and after cycle tests. There are no impurity peaks from the whole XRD patterns, which indicate that ub-Si still keeps its monocrystallinity after being tested for ten times. Figure S11, Supporting Information, shows the SEM pictures before and after the cycle test. It indicates that the structure of ub-Si has not been destroyed at all, and this is the reason why it can keep the reflection and absorption properties no decrease.

To better understand the interaction between the ub-Si structure and light, we construct a simplified model with ordered nanostructure for the FDTD simulation, and the structure feature size is extracted from Figure 1 and Figure S3, Supporting Information. Figure 5a shows the FDTD simulation model of the ub-Si structure. In this model, 25 tetrahedral-pyramids are uniformly distributed on the Si substrate. Figure 5b shows the reflectance results belong to a FDTD simulation result compared to the experimental measurement. The results agree well, indicating that our model can be used for investigating the interaction between the ub-Si structure and light. For the ub-Si material, the absorption ability of electromagnetic power can be used as a simple function to calculate^[30,40,41]

$$P_{\text{abs}} = \frac{1}{2} \omega \cdot \text{Im}(\epsilon_{\text{Si}}) \cdot |E|^2 \quad (4)$$

where P_{abs} is the absorption ability, $|E|$ stands for the amplitude of the total electric field intensity inside ub-Si and $|E|^2$ states for field enhancement, $\text{Im}(\epsilon_{\text{Si}})$ belongs to the imaginary part of permittivity, and ω represents for the angular frequency. In this given ub-Si sample, ω is $2\pi c/\lambda$. Thus, $\text{Im}(\epsilon_{\text{Si}})$ and $|E|^2$ determine absorption ability together. The data of $\text{Im}(\epsilon_{\text{Si}})$ can be found in the study by Ma et al.^[30] There it is indicated that the value of $\text{Im}(\epsilon_{\text{Si}})$ sharply reduces from wavelength 300 to 500 nm and the wavelength larger than 500 nm keeps at a constant. This means that the ub-Si absorption ability is only decided by field enhancement $|E|^2$ when the wavelength of incident light exceeds 500 nm. Figure 5c–f shows the EFE of a pyramidal nanostructure changes from ub-Si/vacuum interface to the inner ub-Si under different light wavelengths. As shown in Figure 5c, the light wavelength at 300 nm interacts strongly with the interfaces of the ub-Si, resulting in a relatively big reflection (see Figure 5b).

Figure 5. Nearly perfect absorption of the ub-Si nanostructure. a) FDTD simulation model of the ub-Si structure. b) Total reflectance of experimental and simulated ub-Si. c–f) EFE of single pyramidal ub-Si nanostructure at a broadband range from UV light (300 nm) to visible light (500 nm) to near infrared (NIR) light (800 nm) to middle IR light (2000 nm).

As the wavelength increases (Figure 5d–f), the interaction gradually becomes weaker and weaker on the ub-Si surface. However, the EFE within the ub-Si tends to become stronger, which means the interaction between light and silicon is enhanced within the ub-Si structures. According to Equation (4), the absorption should be improved compared with wavelength at 300 nm. In fact, it is in accordance with both the experimental measurement and simulated result. It is also clear that the EFE is around up to five times within the ub-Si, confirming the strong light-trapping ability of the structures.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we demonstrate that the ub-Si sample can be applied as an excellent light absorber for a photothermal water evaporation system. The ub-Si sample gains extremely high light absorption of about 98.7% across the full solar spectrum, due to the surface texturing and doping effects. Using the ub-Si sample by connecting with the SPS, we can achieve an average PTCE of 72.96% under 1 sun (AM 1.5G). The ub-Si@SPS photothermal converter has an advanced PTCE compared with the latest reported photothermal conversion materials. It also presents good stability during 10 cycle tests, which indicates a great potentially practical application. Furthermore, FDTD simulations are conducted to get a better understanding of the reflection results and the mechanism of how the EFE affects the light absorption. The reported nontoxic, highly efficient, cost-efficiently, and broadband-solar-spectrum absorptive ub-Si photothermal material is expected to provide wide promising

applications such as water purification, photothermal therapy, and photothermoelectric conversion.

4. Experimental Section

Materials and Reagents. Of note, 4 in. (100) oriented p-type silicon wafers (B doped, 0.01–0.02 Ω cm) were purchased from SIEGERT WAFER GMBH. Deionized (DI) water (18.2 Ω cm) was produced by a laboratory ultrapure water machine. SPS was purchased from Greenet Company. It had plenty of pores and channels with the sizes from several micrometers to several millimeters. Piranha solution (H₂SO₄:H₂O₂ = 3:1, v/v), 5 wt.% hydrofluoric (HF) acid solution was used for the chemical treatments.

Fabrication of ub-Si Nanostructures. The ub-Si nanostructures were fabricated by RIE (Oxford instrument plasma lab 100) with a self-masking dry-etching method according to our previous report.^[32] Then, 4 in. highly B-doped monocrystalline Si wafers (p-type, thickness of 525 ± 20 μm) with a resistivity of 0.01–0.02 Ω cm were used to prepare the ub-Si nanostructures. The structure height can be controlled by the etching time. We chose ub-Si nanostructures etched for 120 min as the photothermal conversion material due to its most remarkable light-trapping performance among the silicon samples with an etching time of 0, 20, 30, 40, 60, and 120 min. The cleaning process for silicon samples was using a standard buffered oxide etch (BOE) process, followed by piranha solution and HF solution successively.

Fabrication of the Black Silicon Nanostructures-Based Photothermal Water Evaporation Device. An exposed geometric area of 2 × 2 cm² ub-Si sample was directly placed on the center of the SPS (3 × 3 cm² with saturated water) (as shown in the Results and Discussion section) without any further treatments. The ub-Si together with the SPS (ub-Si@SPS) was placed in the center of the beaker. After that, DI water was slowly added into the beaker to reach about 80% height of the SPS. The remaining height of SPS was kept to ensure enough channels for efficient water evaporation. Xe lamp (LOT, quantum design) was used as the light source. For cycle

test, the experiments were repeated ten times under 100 mW cm^{-2} of AM 1.5G irradiation. The same mass of water was used for evaporation at each time, and before irradiation, the experimental setup was naturally cooled to room temperature. The mass loss of evaporated water was recorded by the balance under the beaker. All the evaporation experiments had been conducted at room temperature ($22^\circ\text{C} \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$) with a humidity of $30\% \pm 5\%$.

Characterization: SEM pictures were obtained by a cold field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Hitachi S-4800 SEM). TEM characterizations were conducted by a spherical aberration-corrected TEM (JEOL JEM-ARM200F) with a CETCOR image corrector (CEOS GmbH) at 200 kV. The crystallographic phases of the Si and ub-Si were tested using a SIEMENS/BRUKER D5000 X-ray diffractometer (XRD), employing Cu $K\alpha$ radiation. OM images were taken with a Zeiss OM. Raman measurements were conducted using a NTEGRA Spectra (Spectrum Instruments Limited). UV-Vis-NIR reflectance experiments were tested with an UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Cary 5000). Wettability tests were conducted with a Drop Shape Analysis System (Krüss DSA 10 Mk2).

FDTD Simulation: The reflectance and EFE simulations were conducted by using a FDTD method based on the software package Lumerical FDTD solutions.^[42] A simplified model with a periodic unit cell of the pyramidal ub-Si structure was constructed and simulated. Four sides pyramids with the dimension of $1.6 \mu\text{m} \times 1.6 \mu\text{m} \times 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ were used. For the x and y direction, the periodic condition was used for all cell boundaries. For the z -direction, a perfectly matched layer was used between the Si substrate and ub-Si. For the reflectance and EFE simulations, the ub-Si was illuminated by a total field scattered field source with wavelengths of 300 to 2500 nm.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

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broadband absorption, photothermal conversion, solar energy harvesting, ultrablack silicon structure, water evaporation

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